

VICTIMOLOGICAL PREVENTION OF OFFENSES COMMITTED WITHIN THE FAMILY AND HOUSEHOLD SPHERE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15314666>

Abstract. This article highlights the factors contributing to offenses committed within the sphere of family and domestic relations, their causes and conditions, as well as the problems arising in the field of victimological prevention and ways to address them. Additionally, it outlines the main directions for improving the spiritual and moral environment within the family.

Keywords: Family and domestic relations, offenses, victimological prevention of offenses, measures, prevention, causes and conditions, ways of elimination, problems, conflict situations.

According to World Health Organization statistics, 736 million women have experienced physical or sexual violence from their spouse or another person at least once in their lives.

Of these, more than 640 million (87%) women and girls over 15 years of age were subjected to aggressive behavior from partners.

Economic violence is also observed in 98% of relationships where any other type of violence exists.

94-99 percent of victims of domestic violence experienced various forms of economic violence. 60 percent of them lost their jobs due to pressure from their partner.

95% of men who use physical violence also use psychological violence.

As a rule, women who committed murders were subjected to threats, beatings, and insults from their partners for many years.

Men who are aggressive towards women often treat children the same way[1].

Victimological prevention of offenses committed within the framework of family and domestic relations is understood as the activity of the body or institution directly carrying out the prevention of offenses, aimed at applying preventive measures aimed at reducing the risk of becoming a victim of offenses arising in personal relations between spouses, parents and children, bride and groom and father-in-law and mother-in-law, brother-in-law and sister-in-law, grandparents and grandchildren, brothers and sisters, adoptive and adopted, relations between neighbors and similar relatives - primarily between persons connected by marriage, blood relations or family ties[2].

In our country, more than 30 thousand divorces are registered annually, and more than 70 percent of those who apply to the courts on these issues have an unhealthy socio-psychological atmosphere in their families, disagreements and conflicts between spouses, mothers-in-law and daughters-in-law.

According to the analysis of 2024, today 28% of crimes against the life and health of a person, in particular, 28% of murders, 20% of intentional bodily harm, 12.5% of insults and slander, are committed within the framework of family and marital relations[3]. That is why the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev said: "I personally am deeply

troubled by the fact that there are unhealthy relationships in families, quarrels between mothers-in-law and daughters-in-law, husbands and wives, and cases of suicide among our women." [4], – he emphasized.

Within the framework of research on the prevention of domestic offenses, the opinions of scientists on the types of domestic violence can be divided into the following groups:

Scientists of the first group tried to study the fact that domestic violence is mainly committed through the use of physical force and their characteristics. Violence manifests itself in the intentional use of physical violence against another person, aimed at harming the health or life of a person, violating their physical inviolability.

Scientists of the second group tried to substantiate in their research that domestic violence occurs under the influence of psychological dominance and the characteristics inherent in them. Violence is the commission of actions aimed at influencing the psyche of a person by various means, causing psychological tension, and restricting the honor, dignity, and freedom of a person.

Scientists of the third group believe that sexual violence in the process of family life occurs as a result of certain criminogenic factors and is tragic in that it is committed against family members and relatives in the family [5].

Prevention inspectors organize and carry out victimological prevention of offenses within the framework of family and domestic relations in order to reduce the probability of citizens or certain individuals becoming victims of offenses within the framework of family and domestic relations in the administrative territory.

When carrying out general victimological prevention, it is necessary to take into account the need to neutralize and eliminate conflicts in society that contribute to domestic violence in general, and in particular, to eliminate conflicts in the personal relationships of family members.

neutralization and prevention of contradictions, as well as identification and work with latent victims, suppression of victimization processes and measures for the protection and rehabilitation of victims.

In the implementation of special victimological prevention, law enforcement agencies, primarily internal affairs bodies, are considered subjects of special victimological prevention. The implementation of victimological crime prevention activities is the responsibility of prevention inspectors.

To increase the effectiveness of the activities of crime prevention inspectors in the field of victimological crime prevention, it is necessary to carry out work in the following areas:

- the role of the victims in the commission of the offense, as well as the causes and possibilities of the victim's actions;
- identification and elimination of conditions;
- conducting awareness-raising work to reduce the likelihood of victimization of persons living in dysfunctional families;
- identification of categories of persons most likely to be victims of domestic violence;
- development of preventive measures based on the individual and socio-psychological characteristics of victims of offenses.

In conclusion, it can be said that the organization of activities for the prevention of offenses within the family-domestic sphere:

firstly, timely identification of individuals leading antisocial lifestyles and families in socially dangerous situations;

secondly, to be aware of antisocial phenomena and processes, events and phenomena;

thirdly, raising the legal awareness and culture of citizens;

fourthly, it allows for the implementation of comprehensive socio-legal measures aimed at eliminating, weakening, and preventing offenses of this type.

This, first of all, contributes to the early prevention of offenses, their neutralization, influencing persons who may commit offenses, and preventing various encroachments on the life and health of citizens.

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